

Studies in Catalytic Dehydrogenation. Part VII. Synthesis and Dehydrogenation of Spiro-[6,4]undecanes

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Synthesis of 7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane and its alkyl derivatives have been described. When heated with Pd-C at 380-400° in a sealed tube, dehydrogenation of these spirans accompanied by ring transformation occurs, affording an anthracene or a phenanthrene derivative as the main product.

The synthesis and catalytic dehydrogenation of a large number spiro-(5,4)decane had been described in earlier papers¹ in this series. There we had noted that the catalytic dehydrogenation of these spirans, which contain a six-carbon ring system and a five-carbon ring system with a common carbon atom, took place with ring transformation when heated with Pd-C at 300-330°. No carbon atom was lost from the spiro-ring during dehydrogenation. We have now synthesised several spiro-(6,4)undecanes, that is, spirans with a seven-carbon ring system and a five-carbon ring system with a common carbon atom, with a view to studying the catalytic dehydrogenation of these compounds. It has been found that these spirans are not affected when heated with Pd-C catalyst at 350° in a metal bath, but dehydrogenation accompanied by ring transformation occurs only when heated with Pd-C in a sealed tube at 380-400°. Under this condition 7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: R₁=R₂=H) gave anthracene as the main dehydrogenation product along with traces of *o*-xylene. 3'-Methyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: R₁=Me; R₂=H) gave on dehydrogenation mainly 2-methylanthracene and a small amount of 1, 2, 4-trimethylbenzene. 3'-Ethyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: R₁=Et; R₂=H) gave 2-ethylanthracene as the only dehydrogenation product. It has, however, been found that 2-methyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: R₁=H; R₂=Me) gave 2-methylphenanthrene and *o*-xylene as the dehydrogenation products; no anthracene derivative could be detected. In all these cases, it is noted that during dehydrogenation contraction of the seven-carbon ring system takes place along with the rearrangement of the cyclopentane ring, furnishing ultimately anthracene or phenanthrene derivative, with a loss of a carbon atom.

Though it is very difficult to explain satisfactorily the exact mechanism of the reaction, the following steps may possibly interpret the course of the reaction. The seven-carbon ring in the spiran (IV) first opens up, as shown in (V), affording the intermediate radical (VI), which then ring-closes with the formation of a naphthalene derivative with an angular methyl group and a cyclopentane ring in spiran formation (VII). The cyclopentane ring now opens up and its ring closes either in a linear or in an angular manner with the formation of a new six-carbon ring and on aromatisation gives rise ultimately to an anthracene or a phenanthrene derivative by loss of the angular methyl group.

It is evident that during dehydrogenation the intermediate (VII: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$) opens along the dotted lines away from the methyl group in the cyclopentane ring. It then ring-closes in an angular manner, yielding ultimately 2-methylphenanthrene. Similar opening of cyclopentane ring away from the methyl group in similar spirocyclic compounds was noted by Sen Gupta and Chatterjee². In all the three other cases, where there is no alkyl substituent in the spiro-(6,4)undecane ring system, anthracene derivatives are obtained as the dehydrogenation products and no phenanthrene.

The formation of a little *o*-xylene or 1,3,4-trimethylbenzene as dehydrogenation products can be explained by assuming that the seven-carbon ring system in the spiran opens along the dotted lines as shown in (V).

The four spiro-hydrocarbons, required for dehydrogenation experiments, have been synthesised from substituted δ -arylvaleric acid by an extension of the method we had followed earlier³ for the synthesis of benzuberans. For the synthesis of 7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: $R_1=R_2=H$), anhydride of cyclopentane-1,1-diacetic acid was condensed with benzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, affording $\beta\beta$ -cyclopentane- γ -benzoylbutyric acid (I: $R_1=R_2=H$). The keto-acid on the Clemmensen reduction gave $\beta\beta$ -cyclopentane- δ -phenylvaleric acid (II: $R_1=R_2=H$), which was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid mixture, yielding 7,8-benzo-9-keto-spiro-(6,4)undecane (III: $R_1=R_2=H$). The spiro-ketone on the Clemmensen reduction gave 7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: $R_1=R_2=H$).

2. This *Journal*, 1954, 31, 11.

3. Sen Gupta and Sen, this *issue*, p. 653.

In a similar manner, 3'-methyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$) and 3'-ethyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$) have been synthesised from toluene and anhydride of cyclopentane-1,1-diacetic acid and from ethylbenzene and anhydride of cyclopentane-1,1-diacetic acid respectively. Formation of terephthalic acid by alkaline permanganate oxidation of the keto-acids (I: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$) and (I: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$) gave a definite proof that the Friedel-Crafts reaction took place at the *para* position of the substituted benzenoid substrates. 2-Methyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$) has been synthesised similarly, starting from benzene and anhydride of 3-methylcyclopentane-1,1-diacetic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

7,8-Benzo-spiro-(6,4) undecane

$\beta\beta$ -Cyclopentane- γ -benzoylbutyric acid (I: $R_1=R_2=H$) and $\beta\beta$ -cyclopentane- δ -phenylvaleric acid (II: $R_1=R_2=H$) were prepared according to Ali *et al.*⁴. The valeric acid (II: $R_1=R_2=H$) was purified by distillation under reduced pressure, b.p. 195-96°/6 mm.

7,8-Benzo-9-keto-spiro-(6,4)undecane (III: $R_1=R_2=H$).—The valeric acid (II: $R_1=R_2=H$; 5 g.) was mixed with polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 30 g. and 89% H_3PO_4 , 30 ml) and was heated on a steam bath for 1½ hours with stirring. The product was poured on crushed ice and the spiro-ketone was extracted with ether, washed with ammonia, dried with sodium sulphate, and distilled as a light straw-coloured liquid, b.p. 192-95°/16 mm, which soon solidified. It was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 57-58°, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 83.8; H, 8.2. $C_{13}H_{18}O$ requires C, 84.11; H, 8.41%).

The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 200° (decomp.). (Found: C, 70.6; H, 7.61; N, 15.6. $C_{16}H_{21}ON_3$ requires C, 70.84; H, 7.74; N, 15.49%).

7,8-Benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: $R_1=R_2=H$).—The spiro-ketone (III: $R_1=R_2=H$; 5 g.) was boiled with amalgamated zinc (20 g.) and HCl (conc., 20 ml) for 24 hours. The product was obtained as a colorless liquid with a fragrance, b.p. 153-55°/7 mm, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 90.1; H, 9.8. $C_{13}H_{20}$ requires C, 90.0; H, 10.0%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV: $R_1=R_2=H$).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2.5 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.25 g.) in a sealed pyrex tube at 380-400° for 18 hours. While opening the sealed tube, the issuing gas burnt with a blue flame. The product was extracted with ether, solvent removed, and the residual oil was subjected to chromatographic fractionation on Brockmann alumina with hexane. Eluates, each 10 ml, were collected. The first and second eluates contained oily residue with odour like xylene, after removal of the solvent. The oily residues were mixed together and distilled. The liquid distilled at 145°. It was oxidised by means of alkaline permanganate solution and the product was identified as phthalic acid, m.p. 200° (decomp.). The anhydride of the acid had m.p. 130°.

The third, fourth, fifth, and sixth eluates, each, contained a small quantity of a solid after removal of the solvent. Trinitrobenzene derivative was prepared separately with the solids from each eluate. They melted in the range between 155° and 160°. Trinitrobenzene derivatives were mixed together and crystallised repeatedly from rectified spirit as orange-coloured needles, m.p. 161°. The mixed m.p. with the T. N. B. derivative of an authentic sample of anthracene was not depressed. (Found: C, 61.1; H, 4.2. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{13}O_6N_3$: C, 61.35; H, 3.32%).

The hydrocarbon was regenerated from T. N. B. derivative and crystallised from ethanol in colorless flakes, m.p. 216°. The mixed m. p. with a sample of anthracene remained unaltered. (Found: C, 94.2; H, 5.45. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}$: C, 94.38; H, 5.61%).

3'-Methyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane

$\beta\beta$ -Cyclopentane- γ -(p-toluy)butyric acid (I: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$) was prepared from anhydride of cyclopentane-1,1-diacetic acid (45 g.), toluene (100 ml), and aluminium chloride (110 g.) exactly as in the case of the keto-acid (I: $R_1=R_2=H$). It was crystallised from hexane, m.p. 58°, yield 48 g. (Found: C, 73.76; H, 7.48. $C_{16}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 73.84; H, 7.69%).

The semicarbazone crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 207-208°. (Found: C, 64.1; H, 7.31; N, 13.12. $C_{17}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires C, 64.35; H, 7.25; N, 13.24%).

Oxidation of the Keto-acid (I: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$).—The keto-acid was oxidised by heating with an alkaline permanganate solution. The oxidation product was crystallised from HCl (conc.). The acid was characterised as terephthalic acid. It gave methyl ester, m.p. 140°.

$\beta\beta$ -Cyclopentane- δ -(p-tolyl)valeric Acid (II: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$).—The butyric acid (I: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$; 30 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (120 g.) and HCl (conc., 120 ml) for 24 hours. The reduced acid had b.p. 175°/1 mm, yield 18 g. (Found: C, 78.21; H, 8.82. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04; H, 8.94%).

3'-Methyl-7,8-benzo-9-keto-spiro-(6,4)undecane (III: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$).—The valeric acid (II: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$; 9 g.) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 90 g. and 89% H_3PO_4 , 90 ml) as in the preparation of the keto-spiran (III: $R_1=R_2=H$). It is a light straw-coloured liquid, b.p. 185-87°/7 mm, yield 5.5 g. (Found: C, 83.9; H, 8.6. $C_{16}H_{20}O$ requires C, 84.21; H, 8.77%).

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of the spiro-ketone was crystallised from ethyl acetate as orange crystals, m.p. 194-95°. (Found: C, 64.52; H, 5.9; N, 13.58. $C_{22}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires C, 64.70; H, 5.88; N, 13.72%).

3'-Methyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$).—The spiro-ketone (III: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$; 10 g.) was reduced with amalgamated zinc (40 g.) and HCl (conc., 40 ml) for 24 hours. It is a colorless oil, b.p. 145-47°/1 mm; yield 6 g.; d_4^{25} 0.8779, n_D^{25} 1.5415, $(R_D)_{25}$ 68.82 (calc. 68.228). (Found: C, 89.48; H, 10.2. $C_{16}H_{22}$ requires C, 89.7; H, 10.28%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV: $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2.5 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.25 g.) in a sealed pyrex tube at 380–400° for 16 hours. The product was subjected to chromatographic fractionation of Brockmann alumina with hexane as in the previous case. The first and second eluates contained oily residues with characteristic odour. The oils did not form any T. N. B. complex. These were mixed together and oxidised with alkaline permanganate solution. An acid was isolated according to the usual method and identified as trimelic acid, m.p. 216° (decomp.).

The third and fourth eluates left a small quantity of solids after removal of the solvent. T. N. B. complex, prepared separately, melted at 125–30°. T. N. B. derivatives were mixed together and crystallised repeatedly from rectified spirit when red-coloured needles, melting at 130°, were obtained. The mixed m.p. with the T. N. B. derivative of an authentic sample of 2-methylantracene was not depressed. (Found: C, 61.89; H, 3.64. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3$: C, 62.22; H, 3.70%).

The hydrocarbon was regenerated from T. N. B. derivatives and crystallised from ethanol in colorless flakes, m. p. 201°. The mixed m. p. with an authentic sample of 2-methylantracene remained unaltered. (Found: C, 93.54; H, 6.1. Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}$: C, 93.75; H, 6.25%).

3'-Ethyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4) undecane

$\beta\beta$ -Cyclopentane- γ -(p-ethylbenzoyl)butyric Acid (I: $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$).—A solution of anhydride of cyclopentane-1,1-diacetic acid (35 g.) in dry ethylbenzene (22 g.) was gradually added with stirring to an ice-cold suspension of powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (60 g.) in dry *sym*-tetrachloroethane. The keto-acid was finally purified by distillation, b.p. 208°/1 mm, yield 52 g. (Found: C, 74.65; H, 7.62. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 74.45; H, 8.02%).

The semicarbazone was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 172–73°. (Found: C, 65.41; H, 7.37; N, 12.61. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires C, 65.25; H, 7.55; N, 12.68%).

Oxidation of the Keto-acid (I: $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$).—The keto-acid was oxidised with an alkaline permanganate solution. The isolated acid was characterised as terephthalic acid.

$\beta\beta$ -Cyclopentane- δ -(p-ethylphenyl)valeric Acid (II: $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$).—The butyric acid (I: $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; 15 g.) was reduced by boiling gently with amalgamated zinc (60 g.) and HCl (conc., 60ml) for 24 hours. The reduced acid was finally purified by distillation, b.p. 190°/1 mm, yield 8 g. (Found: C, 78.25; H, 9.4. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 78.46; H, 9.23%).

3'-Ethyl-7,8-benzo-9-keto-spiro-(6,4)undecane (III: $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$).—The valeric acid (II: $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; 8 g.) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 48 g. and 99% H_3PO_4 , 48ml). The spiro-ketone is a light straw-coloured liquid, b.p. 170°/1 mm, yield 4 g. (Found: C, 84.16; H, 8.82. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.29; H, 9.09%).

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of the spiro-ketone was crystallised from ethyl acetate as orange crystals. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 6.3; N, 13.32. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires C, 65.40; H, 6.16; N, 13.27%).

3'-Ethyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$).—The spiro-ketone (III: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$; 7 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (40 g.) and HCl (conc., 40 ml) for 30 hours. It is a colorless oil, b.p. 155-56°/2 mm, yield 4 g.; d^{25}_4 1.005, n^{25}_D 1.541, $(R_L)_D$ 71.28 (calc. 72.876). (Found: C, 89.15; H, 10.4. $C_{17}H_{24}$ requires C, 89.47; H, 10.52%.)

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2.6 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.26 g.) in a sealed tube at 380-400° for 16 hours. The product was subjected to chromatographic fractionation on Brockmann alumina with hexane. The first and second eluates contained only a small quantity of unaltered spiro-hydrocarbon. The third and fourth eluates gave a pale yellow oil. The later eluates did not contain any residue. Oils obtained in the third and fourth eluates were separately converted into T.N.B. complex in ethanolic solution which melted in the range between 110° and 118°. The T.N.B. derivatives were mixed together and crystallised repeatedly from ethanol as red needles, m.p. 119-20°. (Found: C, 62.80; H, 4.08. $C_{22}H_{17}O_6N_3$ requires C, 63.0; H, 4.05%). The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the T.N.B. derivative, m.p. 150-51°. Walmann and Marmorstein⁵ record the m.p. of 2-ethylanthracene as 150-51°.

2-Methyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane

$\beta\beta$ -(3'-Methylcyclopentane)- γ -benzoylbutyric acid (I: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$) was prepared according to Ali *et al*.⁴

$\beta\beta$ -(3'-Methylcyclopentane)- δ -phenylvaleric Acid (II: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—The butyric acid (I: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$; 40 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (160 g.) and HCl (conc., 160 ml). It is a colorless oil, b. p. 188°/1 mm, yield 25 g. (Found: C, 78.2; H, 8.72. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04; H, 8.94%.)

2-Methyl-7,8-benzo-9-keto-spiro-(6,4)undecane (III: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—The valeric acid (II: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$; 24 g.) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 70 g. and 89% H_3PO_4 , 30 ml). The spiro-ketone is a light straw-coloured liquid, b.p. 162-64°/1 mm, yield 14.3 g. (Found: C, 84.1; H, 8.62. $C_{16}H_{20}O$ requires C, 84.21; H, 8.77%.)

The D. N. P. of the spiro-ketone crystallised from ethyl acetate as orange needles, m. p. 206-208°. (Found: C, 64.38; H, 5.63; N, 13.6. $C_{22}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires C, 64.70; H, 5.88; N, 13.72%.)

2-Methyl-7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecane (IV: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—The spiro-ketone (III: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$; 14 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (60 g.) and HCl (conc., 60 ml) for 24 hours. It is a colorless liquid with fragrance, b.p. 135-36°/2 mm, yield 8 g. (Found: C, 89.56; H, 10.14. $C_{16}H_{22}$ requires C, 89.71; H, 10.28%.)

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2.5 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.25 g.) in a sealed tube at 380-400° for 16 hours. The product was subjected to chromatographic fractionation on Brockmann alumina. The first eluate contained no solute. The second, third, and

fourth eluates contained oily residues with an odour like xylene after removal of the solvent. The liquid distilled within 145°. It was oxidised by an alkaline permanganate solution. An acid was isolated and identified as phthalic acid; m.p. 200° (decomp.). The anhydride of the acid melted at 130°.

The fifth, sixth and seventh eluates contained oil with a small quantity of solid on removal of the solvent. Subsequent eluates contained no solute. The residues from the fifth, sixth, and seventh eluates were separately converted into trinitrobenzene complex in ethanol. T. N. B. derivatives separated in each case as orange needles which were mixed together and crystallised repeatedly from ethanol when beautiful orange needles melting at 155-56° were obtained. (Found: C, 62.56; H, 3.74. $C_{21}H_{13}O_6N_3$ requires C, 62.22; H, 3.70%).

The regenerated hydrocarbon crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 55-56°. The mixed m. p. of the hydrocarbon with an authentic sample of 2-methylphenanthrene remained unaltered. (Found: C, 93.49; H, 6.3. Calc for $C_{15}H_{12}$: C, 93.75; H, 6.25%).

The *picrate*, prepared from the purified hydrocarbon, crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 118-19°. (Found: C, 59.68; H, 3.63. $C_{21}H_{15}N_3O_7$ requires C, 59.85; H, 3.56%).

In a brief note⁶ we had indicated previously the direction of the present investigation. The experiments described in this investigation have been carried out in the Chemical Laboratory, Presidency College, Calcutta.

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